

A one-stage modified Tiny-YOLOv3 method for Real time Moroccan license plate recognition

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Abstract—Automatic license plate recognition systems (ALPRS) have a major significant role in supporting smart city initiatives because of their promising applications in various areas, such as road safety, traffic control, smart parking, toll management, and security. Owing to ALPRS's importance, numerous methods have been developed. However, many of the present solutions are still suffering from some inefficiencies in real-world situations, generally related to many constraints. In this work, we address the problem of Moroccan car license plate detection and recognition based on the state-of-the-art YOLO deep learning framework. To this end, we have made improvements in the Tiny-YOLOv3's network structure to make it more rigorous. We proposed a real-time end-to-end ALPRS using a one-stage approach. The network is trained using images from a collected large-scale dataset of Moroccan license plates taken from different real-world scenarios, with the addition of various data augmentation techniques, to ensure robustness and efficiency under different conditions. To improve the generalization ability and accuracy of our system, we also combined the proposed algorithm with the transfer learning technique. Extensive experiments prove that the proposed method achieves an excellent trade-off between speed and accuracy as well as the system executes the detection /recognition process in a single phase with 98.45% of accuracy and 59.5 Frames Per Second (FPS). Also, a comparative evaluation demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed method compared to previous state-of-the-art methods.

Index Terms—Real time Automatic License Plate Recognition, Deep learning, Transfer learning, Data augmentation; Tiny-YOLOv3

I. INTRODUCTION

In a world with strong demographic growth, the number of vehicles is becoming more and more important. This growth poses several problems for the efficient management of large cities: violation of the highway code, accidents, crimes, shortage of parking spaces, traffic jams, etc. In this context, researchers have tried to propose several solutions based on the application of computer techniques to intelligent transport systems. These techniques use image processing algorithms to identify vehicles. This domain is vast, since there are several types of vehicles in a road scene: trailers, trucks, buses, cars, motorcycles, etc. On the other hand, existing research has focused mainly on the automatic detection and recognition of

car license plates. Fig. 1 shows that such a system has four steps [1]:

- Image acquisition: Images can be extracted from video, image collections or cameras,
- License plate detection: extraction of the license plate area according to certain defined characteristics or properties.
- Character segmentation: extraction of numbers and characters from the plate.
- Character recognition: recognition of each character individually to read the license plate.

Fig. 1. Process for a complete ALPRS

Such a system requires a lot of resources and a significant calculation time and also requires to obtain a very good or a perfect result before moving from one step to another [1]. In practice, an insufficient result in one step automatically leads to failure in the next steps [2]. To overcome this problem, Hsu et al [3] reduced the number of steps of an ALPRS to three: in the first, they used the technique of edge clustering to extract the license plate from the image, then based on maximally stable extreme region (MSER) detector, they proposed an efficient method to segment characters from the plate. Finally, they combined the performance of LDA and SVM to recognize characters. Also for the purpose of reducing the number of intermediate steps in an ALPRS, Kessentini et al [4] proposed a two-stage ALPRS framework. They started with the license plate separation with the YOLOv2 [5] method, then in the character recognition phase, they compared the results of two methods: R-CNN [6] and YOLOv2. Taking into consideration the state of the art that we have carried out throughout our research, it has become clear that the emergence of neural networks has largely influenced research in this area. In [7], the authors used Fast YOLO both to detect the license plate and to detect the car. Subsequently, they recognized the characters still using the same method. In the

article by Dong et al. [8], the authors kept the same strategy: a license plate detection step where they used the Fast RPN approach and the R-CNN method and another recognition step which uses a new structure composed of parallel spatial transform networks and shared-weight recognizers. Inspired by Yolo [5], they proposed a method called ALMD-YOLO where they modified the structure of the Yolo model to make it faster and more precise in comparison with the method in [3]. But this approach finds several difficulties in detecting small objects (such as characters) or license plates taken from a far position. Experimental tests have shown that this method is 1.5 times faster with less model size reduced by 57 times. In the system proposed by Li et al [9], the authors relied on Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to learn high-level characteristics in a cascading framework, which improves detection and recognition performance. First, they used CNN to detect the characters. Next, they trained a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with long-short term memory to recognize sequential features extracted from the entire license plate via the CNNs. This method exceeds by 2% of precision the edge-based method used in Hsu et al [3], however, concerning the speed of calculation, the method of Li et al [9] requires 2-3 s, while the approach Hsu et al [3] requires only 260 ms on average. So we can conclude that this method which also adopts two steps does not solve the problem of computing time. Nevertheless, the authors performed recognition on Chinese characters, English numbers and letters, using limited training data.

From the literature, it can be said that, on the one hand, researchers make extensive use of CNN-based methods to achieve impressive detection results. This research investigated the performance of CNN models, including their variants such as: YOLO [5], SSD [10], R-CNN [6] and R-FCN [11]. On the other hand, the majority of research works only deal with part of the ALPRS pipeline (LP detection for example) or perform their experiments on databases that do not reflect real world scenarios. Therefore, it is difficult to accurately assess the proposed methods. In addition, several works are carried out on plates which contain only Latin letters which makes the task of recognition easy. surely, processing license plates in other languages is difficult, but the characters in Moroccan LPs are even more difficult because Arabic characters have many complexities such as a dot on or under certain letters (like "ب"), A short mark on some letters (like "أ"), etc. Apart from all these motivations, To our knowledge, this is the first study to address the issue of detection and recognition of Moroccan license plates.

Motivated by this statement, in this article we propose an end-to-end deep learning system for Moroccan car license plate recognition. Our main goal is to reduce computing time. The idea is to present an approach that uses only one step, unlike other systems that use one for detection and another for recognition. Thus, our method achieves high precision in complex environments while taking into account the constraints of a real-time system. This article presents,

mainly, the contributions below:

- A real-time end-to-end ALPRS is proposed using a one-step approach for the detection and recognition of Moroccan LPs. The detection system is based on the popular Tiny-YOLOv3 CNN object detector.
- A Moroccan LP image dataset with 1663 annotated images from different real world scenarios is introduced.
- We have exploited the benefits of data augmentation to increase the training dataset.
- We combined our algorithm with transfer learning to improve the generalization ability and accuracy of our license plate recognition system.
- A comparative evaluation between the proposed method and previous state-of-the-art methods is carried out.

This document is composed of the following sections: Section 2 details the proposed method based on YOLO. Section 3 describes our Moroccan car license plate database. Section 4 contains experimental results and discussion while Section 5 concludes the article.

II. THE MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, we will describe our system consisting of a single step which aims to do the detection and recognition of Moroccan license plates. This system is based on the Tiny-YOLOv3 approach[12].

Most researchers, especially those who have proposed methods based on machine learning techniques, have found it difficult to detect small characters. For this reason, they resorted to dividing their systems into two phases: a detection phase to extract the license plate and a recognition phase to recognize characters from the license plate. This technique will surely detect characters easily since they occupy a large part of the cropped image. On the other hand, these systems have two drawbacks:

- In case they fail to detect the license plate, character recognition will be impossible,
- such a system made up of two parts performs a double calculation which requires more resources.

In this context, and to avoid these drawbacks, we propose an approach composed of a single phase. our system detects and recognizes the license plate and the characters that compose it simultaneously. This system requires fewer resources and performs fewer calculations.

A. YOLO-v3

In this article, we have chosen to modify the architecture of YOLO-v3 [12]. Unlike Faster R-CNN [6], which uses Region Proposal Network (RPN), YOLO-v3 which is an evolution of YOLO-v1 [5] and YOLO-v2 [13] trains to do classification and bounding box regression simultaneously. this explains why YOLO-v1 is faster than Faster R-CNN but less precise. To solve this problem, YOLO-v2 added other concepts such as "anchor box" and "k-means clustering" to generate a list of predefined boxes that better represent objects. YOLO-v2 also adopts batch normalization, high-resolution classifier, dimension clusters, direct location prediction, fine-grained features,

multi-scale training and other methods which greatly improve the detection accuracy compared to YOLO.

YOLO-v3 is the successor of YOLO-v2. It uses multi-scale prediction to detect the final target, it has a more complex network structure. YOLO-v3 predicts bounding boxes on different scales using Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN). This makes YOLO-v3 more appropriate for detecting small targets. On a standard computer equipped with a GPU, YOLOv3 can easily achieve real-time performance. However, YOLOv3 is very resource-intensive and often runs slowly on miniaturized embedded devices. Tiny-YOLOv3 network can mainly meet real-time requirements on limited hardware resources[14]. Taking into consideration the above discussion, we have decided to improve the Tiny-YOLOv3 algorithm.

B. Tiny-YOLO-v3

The Tiny-YOLOv3 model is a simplified version of the YOLOv3. YOLOv3 uses the architecture of darknet53, and then uses many 1×1 and 3×3 convolution kernels to extract features. Tiny-YOLOv3 reduces the number of convolutional layers, its basic structure has only 7 convolutional layers, and then features are extracted by using a small number of 1×1 and 3×3 convolutional layers. Tiny-YOLOv3 uses the pooling layer instead of YOLOv3's convolutional layer with a step size of 2 to achieve dimensionality reduction, this implies that Tiny-YOLOv3 does not require a large amount of memory, reducing the need for hardware. Tiny-YOLOv3 architecture is shown in (Fig. 2)(a).

C. Proposed method

Most of the previous studies deal with two-step detection and recognition. First, they detect the license plate, they crop it and then they detect the characters. This system is very complicated, it requires more resources to perform the calculations and more time during execution. Our proposed system can handle detection and recognition at the same time in one framework. It takes the input image, detects, and recognizes LPs using the improved Tiny-YOLOv3 architecture, and outputs the cropped plate image with a text file containing all characters. The diagram flowchart of our system can be viewed in (Fig. 6).

Detecting small targets is an important challenge that usually results in the failure of traditional detectors. Multi-scale prediction is an essential step for recognizing various objects, especially small targets, and their disposition observed in a scene.

The Tiny-YOLOv3 implements a two scales FPN with robust semantics. This is done through subsampling layers and a fusion approach. As illustrated in Fig. 2 (a), the sizes of the two scales are 13×13 and 26×26 , which are obtained in the detection of ordinary size targets, respectively.

LPs characters normally, occupy a small portion of the whole image (small targets). Considering accuracy and real-time performance, in this work, we present an improved FPN based three-scale prediction framework to address that problem. On the other hand, inspired from ResNet [15], we introduce 1×1

convolution kernel in the network. From one hand, it reduces the computational complexity and saves memory resources. At the same time, it increases the nonlinear excitation function and enhances the feature extraction capability of the network which can improve detection accuracy. The network structure of the improved network is shown in Fig. 2 (b).

III. DATASET

To test the reliability of our method we must apply it to a database. In our case, and since our system is intended to solve the problem of detection and recognition of Moroccan license plates, we have collected images of real scenes taken from highways, parking lots, the internet, etc ... In addition, and to compare our system to existing ones, we tested it on the AOLP database [3].

A. Specification of Moroccan License Plates

A Moroccan license plate is different from license plates which use Latin letters such as European [16], Brazilian [17] or Chinese [18] plates. LPs that look a bit like Moroccan plates are those that use Arabic or Farsi letters such as Tunisian [19] or Iranian [20] plates.

Moroccan plates consist of three parts separated by vertical lines, in the first part on the left there are five numbers that identify the car, in the middle an Arabic letter and on the right one or two numbers that represent the prefecture or the province where the car has been registered (Fig. 4).

B. Data acquisition

To our knowledge, there is no publicly available database of Moroccan license plates. For this reason, we have created our own database consisting of 1663 images collected under different conditions, namely, different plate colors, non-uniform lighting, different shooting distances, camera angle and type. We also ensured that the photos were taken in different times of the day to ensure the diversity of the data. Fig. 5 shows some examples from our data set.

To build our model, we randomly divided our database: 1165 images for training and 498 images for the test. However, the use of 1165 images in the training phase often results in the phenomenon of "Over-fitting". To remedy this problem, we used several data augmentation techniques. The first method used is that of Afifi et al. [21]. In this method the authors used deep learning to modify the white balance (WB) of an sRGB image. As cited in [21], the principle of Wb is often employed in the field of photography to ensure that the objects which are in an image have the same color even if they are taken in different lighting conditions. This technique may also be beneficial for computer vision applications, among others, object recognition. This is confirmed by an experimental evaluation on our dataset for the recognition of Moroccan license plates. Fig. 3 shows an example of our data augmentation results.

The images of the cars are taken in different positions in real scenes. This implies that the license plates will have several shapes as if they have undergone several transformations. For

Fig. 2. (a) The structure of Tiny-YOLOv3 (b) Improved Tiny-YOLOv3 structure

Fig. 3. An example of our data augmentation results

Fig. 4. Moroccan Licence Plate structure

this reason, we have thought of working with the `imgaug` library [22] which is a library dealing with image augmentation for machine learning experiments. It applies transformations, like rotating to the right or to the left, inserting noise, flipping the image, and also modifies the contrast as well as brightness.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Training of YOLO needs powerful graphical processing unit (GPU). All the experiments were performed on the publicly

Fig. 5. Sample of database images

available Google Colaboratory¹ to provide faster performance in training our model. It is a free Jupyter notebook environment that runs on the cloud.

A. Experimentation with transfer learning

The YOLO model is previously trained on 80 classes, but in our proposed method, we intended to detect and recognize LP classes. To match the number of classes in our system, we had to change the number of digital filters in the last layer. The formula to calculate the filters is shown in the following equation:

$$Filters = (classes + coords + 1) \times \langle number\ of\ mask \rangle \quad (1)$$

Generally, *filters* depend on the classes, *coords*, and number of masks, where mask corresponds to the anchor indices. In

¹<https://colab.research.google.com/>

Fig. 6. The diagram flowchart of our system

our case, we have 16 classes: 10 numerical digits, 5 Arabic letters, and one plate class. consequently, we have to define filters=63. Fig. 7 shows our training validation loss for digits, letters, and the plate. The training model converges after 700 iterations and is stable for the rest of the training phase. The average validation loss is 0.24. In this work, we use our

parameters to a new model to help it in the training phase, in some ways to speed up and optimize the learning efficiency. In our case, pre-training is carried out on the public data set SVHN [23] firstly, and then on our special data set. To test the effectiveness of our proposed method we do two kinds of experiments. On the one hand, we compare the performance of our approach against the original Tiny-YOLOv3 network. On the other hand, we verify the behavior of transfer learning combined with the two networks. The results are shown in Table I.

Fig. 7. Training loss and Validation mAP

proposed deep learning algorithm in conjunction with transfer learning. This will improve the generalization capability and the efficiency of the LP recognition system. Transfer learning [16], as the name suggests, simply migrates pre-trained model

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF VARIOUS ALGORITHM TEST RESULTS.

Network	Accuracy
Tiny-YOLOv3	76.52 %
Proposed	91.83 %
Tiny-YOLOv3 +Transfer learning	92.54 %
Proposed +Transfer learning	98.45 %

Comparing the results of the table above, the method of this article obtained good performance. Without transfer learning, the accuracy value of the proposed network reached 91.83% which is 15.31% higher than that of Tiny-YOLOv3. This could be justified by the addition of layers to multiscale detection. Hence, we can say that the improved architecture is systematically outperforming the original Tiny-YOLOv3 network. When small objects are included (case of LP characters). Also, from the Table I and Fig. 7, we can find out that transfer learning can make the network converge quickly and achieve high accuracy with the two networks: Tiny-YOLOv3 and the proposed improved network.

For better accuracy and highest Intersection over Union (IoU), we used our own anchor boxes created using the K-Means algorithm. IoU is a very important evaluation measure which allows to evaluate the accuracy of an object detector. It

compares the ground truth to the assumed detection. Ideally, we should have a complete overlap, i.e. IoU should approach 1. Generally, an $IOU > 0.7$ can be considered as a satisfactory result. In our case, the proposed model achieves better performance under IoU (0.83) in comparison with Tiny- YOLOv3 (0.75), which means that LP areas detected by our network are closer to the ground truth. The use of anchor boxes greatly facilitates the learning process, allowing multi-scale detection by specifying anchor boxes of varying sizes. Also, a 1×1 convolutional layers are added in the model in the fifth and sixth convolutional layers of the Tiny-YOLOv3 model. To show the effect of adding 1×1 convolutional layer, we show in Table II the mean average precision (mAP) and FPS of three networks.

TABLE II
THE MAP AND THE COMPUTATIONAL TIME REQUIRED OF VARIOUS ALGORITHM.

Network	mAP (%)	FPS
Tiny-YOLOv3	92.54	62.3
Tiny-YOLOv3 +(conv 1x1)	94.08	61.7
Proposed	98.45	59.5

Note that the video functionality was tested on videos recorded on a HUAWEI Y9 (2019) with 30 FPS and video dimensions 1280×720 , which are much lower than the dimensions of the original training data. As Table 2 clearly shows, the mAPs of the proposed network and Tiny-YOLOv3 + (conv 1×1) are significantly higher than those of Tiny-YOLOv3, Using the Tiny-YOLOv3 network, targets are not detected satisfactorily in testing images. In addition, when the structure of this network is improved (Tiny-YOLOv3 + (conv 1×1)), the precision (mAP) increases to 94.8%, but this remains insufficient. On the other hand, the three scales and K-means ++ clustering used in the improved network to change the anchors, clearly influenced the target's AP which was able to reach 98.45%. Since in Tiny-YOLOv3, the most important convolutional layers are the first seven, and the number of layers increases, therefore automatically the number of convolution kernels in the convolutional layer also increases. In fact, the amount of calculation increases during detection, and the FPS is reduced from 62.3 frames to 61.7 frames for Tiny-YOLOv3+(conv 1×1) and 59.5 frames for our proposed network. Despite this, our algorithm still meets the requirements of real-time systems.

In order to prove the effectiveness and the validity of our approach, we have collected a set of videos of real road scenes and we have selected different images. The results of the detection are shown in Fig. 8 We can see that the proposed network can detect small objects such as far LPs. This demonstrates that the improvement we have proposed works well even for complex real-time road environments.

B. Comparison with state-of-the-arts ALPRS

To compare the proposed system with the state-of-the-art ALPRS, we have conducted experiments on the AOLP public dataset [3], which has 2049 images of Taiwan LPs.

Fig. 8. ALPRS results

This dataset is divided into categories with three types of difficulties: road patrol (RP), access control (AC), and traffic law enforcement (LE).

The detection results of our LP detection system are compared to three state-of-the art LP detection systems. To properly evaluate all methods, we used the same training and test sets. We present in Table 3 the character and the plate recognition rates of the proposed method. The obtained results show that our LP recognition approach gives comparable performance in terms of character and LP detection and recognition accuracies. Note that our approach consists of a single stage. Unlike the methods proposed by Hsu et al. [3] and Li et al. [9] which use two-steps: detecting the LP and the recognizing characters from the detected LP. The imperfection of these methods is that having two steps doubles the processing speed and computational complexity.

TABLE III
FONT SIZES FOR PAPERS

Font Size	Appearance (in Times New Roman or Times)		
	Regular	Bold	Italic
8	table caption (in Small Caps), figure caption, reference item		reference item (partial)
9	author email address (in Courier), cell in a table	abstract body	abstract heading (also in Bold)
10	level-1 heading (in Small Caps), paragraph		level-2 heading, level-3 heading, author affiliation
11	author name		
24	title		

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a robust real-time ALPRS using a pipeline with a single deep learning stage for Moroccan LPs. Our system simultaneously detects and recognizes the LP and characters, in fact, the detection speed is faster, and the system is optimized. We modified Tiny-YOLOv3 to create, improved LP detection network. First, we add a

1×1 convolutional kernel to reduce the dimension of the feature, which improve the ability of the model to extract features. This reduces the amount of calculation produced by the deepening model. Second, to further improve performance of the network, the detection scales of Tiny-YOLOv3 have been extended to three to detect the small targets. Finally, since our system meets real-time requirements, in future work we intend to implement it in an embedded system.

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